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TEACHER QUALIFICATIONS, SCHOOL TYPE AND EXPERIENCE AS PREDICTORS OF READING-BASED WRITING INSTRUCTION TECHNIQUES AND RESOURCES IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Reading and writing are recognised as interconnected language skills whose integration in teaching enhances student literacy development. Substantial knowledge gaps exist regarding how teacher characteristics influence the techniques and resources senior secondary school English teachers employ when integrating reading and writing instruction. This descriptive survey examined the techniques and resources that 167 senior secondary English teachers in Ogbomoso, Nigeria employ when using reading to teach writing, with particular attention to how teacher qualifications, teaching experience and school type influence these instructional practices. Teachers comprised 103 from public schools and 64 from private schools, with qualifications ranging from NCE to Master's degrees and experience ranging from less than five years to over ten years. Data were collected via questionnaire with structured items assessing techniques and resources on a four-point Likert scale. Mean and standard deviation described overall technique and resource use, while independent sample t-tests and one-way analysis of variance examined differences based on teacher qualification, experience and school type. Findings revealed that teachers employed a wide range of techniques with overall weighted mean of 3.45 (often to always used), with reading discussion, text organisation and reading models most frequently employed. Teachers consistently utilised resources with weighted mean of 3.50, relying primarily on the English curriculum, textbooks and literature texts. Critically, teacher qualifications significantly influenced both the techniques employed and the range of resources utilised, with Bachelor of Arts in English degree holders demonstrating substantially higher technique use than holders of basic qualifications. Teaching experience also significantly predicted both technique and resource use, with teachers having over ten years of experience employing more varied techniques and resources than less experienced colleagues. School type (public versus private) did not significantly influence either technique or resource selection. This research contributes essential empirical evidence regarding how teacher characteristics influence pedagogical decision-making in Nigerian secondary education, identifies qualification and experience as critical predictors of instructional quality, and informs professional development and teacher preparation policy.

KEYWORDS: English Teachers, Experience, Qualifications, Reading, Resources, Senior Secondary, Techniques, Writing Instruction.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. *The Significance of Writing Development and Reading-Writing Integration*

The declining standards of English language writing among Nigerian secondary school students represent a significant social concern undermining educational outcomes and restricting students' future opportunities. Many senior secondary students demonstrate inadequate writing competencies affecting their academic performance across all subjects while limiting their prospects for higher education and professional advancement (Jacob & Samuel, 2020; Madikiza et al., 2018). This deficiency extends beyond individual achievement; poor writing skills restrict students' capacity to participate effectively in civic discourse, pursue tertiary education opportunities and compete in an increasingly globalised employment market where strong written communication abilities are essential prerequisites.

Contemporary literacy research has established that reading and writing form an interconnected system rather than discrete competencies. Extensive empirical evidence demonstrates that students engaging in systematic reading programmes experience significant improvements in writing fluency, accuracy and organisational sophistication (Krashen, 2004; Nation, 2008). Reading provides essential scaffolding through exposure to diverse genres, writing techniques and language conventions that students subsequently internalise and apply within their own compositions (Ferris & Hedgcock, 2023; Adedokun & Adedokun, 2024). Neurological research reveals that reading and writing engage remarkably similar cognitive processes. Aryanti et al. (2024) utilised advanced neuroimaging techniques demonstrating significant overlap in neural networks involved in reading and writing activities. A comprehensive meta-analysis by Tom-Lawyer and Thomas (2024) established robust correlations between reading comprehension and writing quality, indicating that learners with advanced reading abilities tend to produce more coherent and structured written texts. Furthermore, reading comprehension strategies transfer directly to writing tasks, as both processes engage similar cognitive operations including meaning construction, inference making and text analysis (Fitzgerald & Shanahan, 2000). Through reading, learners encounter various writing styles, grammatical structures and rhetorical strategies (Bamidele et al., 2024) that foster intuitive understanding of how language functions in different communicative

contexts.

1.2. *Teacher Implementation of Reading-Writing Integration*

Despite the established theoretical and empirical benefits of integrating reading and writing instruction, a substantial knowledge gap exists regarding how senior secondary English teachers in Nigerian contexts actually employ techniques and resources to foster this connection. While research documents that integrating reading and writing instruction leads to improvements in students' writing performance, particularly in content, organisation and mechanical accuracy (Ibrahim, 2022; Obabiyi, 2023), such practices remain inconsistently implemented across Nigerian schools (Adebayo, Nduka, Onebunne, Karikari & Obiri, 2024). This implementation inconsistency suggests that teacher-level factors may substantially influence pedagogical choices and instructional quality. Understanding which teacher characteristics predict more sophisticated and varied instructional approaches is therefore essential for enhancing literacy instruction quality.

1.3. *Teacher Qualifications as Influences on Instructional Practice*

The quality of literacy instruction is significantly influenced by teacher qualifications, which encompass both subject matter knowledge and pedagogical preparation. Research establishes that teacher qualifications positively correlate with student achievement in language arts (Wayne & Youngs, 2003; Hill et al., 2005). Teachers with specialised training in literacy education demonstrate greater instructional effectiveness compared to those with generic teacher education backgrounds (Zhang & Zhang, 2024). In the Nigerian context, studies reveal disparities in teacher qualifications across different educational settings. Research indicates that teacher qualifications correlate with the sophistication and range of instructional strategies employed in language teaching (Ezeaku et al., 2025). Teachers with strong subject expertise and pedagogical preparation possess deeper content knowledge enabling them to select and implement more varied and sophisticated techniques for connecting reading and writing instruction. In addition, teachers with higher qualifications may have greater awareness of diverse pedagogical approaches and access to professional development opportunities that enhance their instructional repertoire (Iqbal & Ali, 2024). Specifically, subject-specific qualifications in English

language provide deeper content knowledge enabling teachers to identify multiple connections between reading exemplars and writing strategies, whilst pedagogical qualifications equip teachers with contemporary instructional approaches for making these connections explicit to learners. However, the specific influence of teacher qualifications on the particular techniques and resources teachers employ in Nigerian secondary schools remains under-examined, particularly whether subject knowledge and pedagogical preparation function independently or synergistically.

1.4. Teaching Experience as an Influence on Instructional Practice

Teaching experience represents another critical variable influencing instructional practice and pedagogical decision-making. Experienced teachers typically tend to possess greater pedagogical content knowledge, better classroom management skills and more refined instructional strategies compared to novice teachers (Berliner, 2004; Boyd et al., 2006). In language teaching specifically, experienced teachers are more likely to employ sophisticated techniques for integrating reading and writing instruction through iterative practice allowing them to accumulate diverse pedagogical strategies, understand which techniques address particular learning needs, and refine implementation based on classroom feedback (Tsui, 2003; Farrell, 2012). Experience enables development of practical wisdom, that is, tacit understanding of how to adapt reading-based writing techniques to diverse student populations and classroom contexts. However, research suggests the relationship between experience and effectiveness is not always linear, with benefits potentially plateauing after approximately 5-7 years (Clotfelter, Ladd & Vigdor, 2007; Papay & Kraft, 2015). The quality of experience matters substantially as teachers who engage in continuous professional development and reflective practice demonstrate greater instructional effectiveness regardless of years of service (Day, Sammons & Stobart, 2007; Avalos, 2011). Yet relatively limited empirical evidence exists regarding how experience specifically predicts the range and frequency of reading-based writing techniques and resources employed by Nigerian secondary teachers.

1.5. School Type, Resources and Instructional Practice

School type and resource availability may influence teachers' ability to implement diverse instructional techniques and access varied materials.

Students in schools with adequate learning materials tend to perform better in literacy assessments than those in less favourable settings (Olaitan, 2024). Socioeconomic disparities between types of school compound these differences, with students in well-resourced schools generally outperforming peers in under-resourced schools (Ojeje & Adodo, 2018). In Nigeria specifically, resource allocation and school infrastructure vary across regions and contexts. Inadequate resources such as textbooks, multimedia tools and language laboratories significantly hinder teaching effectiveness (Chigbu & Adamu, 2023; Ononye et al., 2021; Mohammed et al., 2021). However, whether school type (public versus private) fundamentally influences the techniques teachers select for reading-based writing instruction remains unclear, as teachers in both sectors may employ similar pedagogical strategies despite differing resource availability. Empirical investigation of whether school type differentially predicts technique and resource selection is therefore necessary.

1.6. Knowledge Gaps and Research Significance

While research has extensively examined factors influencing literacy instruction in Western educational contexts, a notable scarcity of empirical studies in sub-Saharan African contexts examines how specific teacher characteristics predict the techniques and resources senior secondary English teachers in Nigeria employ for reading-based writing instruction. The academic literature reveals substantial knowledge gaps regarding which teacher characteristics most strongly predict technique variety and sophistication in reading-based writing instruction; how teacher qualifications specifically influence the selection and implementation of particular techniques; whether teaching experience meaningfully predicts the breadth of resources utilised; and whether school type substantially influences pedagogical decision-making. These gaps present constraints on evidence-based professional development planning, teacher preparation program design and educational policy formulation. Empirical evidence regarding which teacher variables predict instructional quality is essential for targeting professional development initiatives and understanding mechanisms through which teacher characteristics influence classroom practice.

1.7. Purpose And Objectives

This study examines the techniques and resources that senior secondary English teachers in Ogbomoso, Nigeria employ when using reading to teach

writing, with primary focus on how teacher qualifications, teaching experience and school type influence these instructional practices. The specific objectives are to identify the techniques senior secondary English teachers employ in using reading to teach writing; find out the resources senior secondary English teachers employ in using reading to teach writing; investigate the influence of teacher qualification on the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing; determine whether teacher qualifications influence the resources employed in using reading to teach writing; assess how school type influences the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing; determine whether school type influences the resources employed in using reading to teach writing; find out whether teaching experience influences the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing; and investigate whether teaching experience influences the resources employed in using reading to teach writing. By addressing these objectives through empirical analysis, the research generates evidence regarding which teacher characteristics predict instructional quality, thereby informing evidence-based professional development initiatives and teacher preparation policy within Nigerian secondary education.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Study Design

This study employed a quantitative research design within a descriptive survey framework which facilitated statistical analysis and valid inferences regarding the characteristics and classroom practices of the target population. The descriptive survey method was selected for its capacity to gather systematic data from large populations using standardised procedures (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018). The study was conducted in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, south-western Nigeria. Ogbomoso is a predominantly Yoruba-speaking urban and semi-urban community comprising five Local Government Areas (LGAs), namely Ogbomoso North, Ogbomoso South, Surulere, Oriire and Ogo-Oluwa. Secondary education in Nigeria is administered under the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014), with senior secondary schools (SSS1 to SSS3) typically serving students between the ages of 15 and 18. English language is a compulsory subject at this level and serves both as a medium of instruction and as a core examination subject in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). Secondary schools in the Ogbomoso metropolis

include both government-owned institutions (state and federal) and privately owned institutions, serving populations with varying socioeconomic backgrounds. This setting provides a representative context for examining English language teaching practices within the Nigerian secondary school system, where persistent challenges in reading and writing proficiency have been widely documented (Adebile 1996; Oluwole, 2008).

2.2. Study Population and Sampling Strategy

The target population comprises all English language teachers in senior secondary schools across Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria. Three of the five Local Government Areas (LGAs), namely Ogbomoso North, Ogbomoso South and Ogo-Oluwa, were randomly selected to form the study area. A purposive sampling strategy was subsequently employed to include all English language teachers within these three LGAs who were actively engaged in senior secondary school instruction, yielding a total sample of 167 teachers, of whom 103 were from public secondary schools and 64 from private secondary schools. Purposive sampling was deemed appropriate given the need to engage participants with direct, relevant experience in secondary school English language teaching, specifically those with active responsibility for developing students' reading and writing skills at the senior secondary level (Patton, 2023). This approach ensured the sample comprised teachers delivering the actual instruction under investigation, rather than including teachers without direct classroom responsibility for reading and writing instruction. The entire accessible population within the selected LGAs was included, thereby eliminating the need for a probability-based sample size calculation and strengthening the representativeness of the findings within the study context. Teachers who did not teach English language at the senior secondary level, or who were not based in the three selected LGAs, were excluded from the study.

2.3. Data Collection

Data was collected using a researcher-developed structured questionnaire comprising three sections. Section A gathered demographic information including gender, educational qualifications, years of teaching experience and school type (public or private). Section B consisted of structured items measured on a four-point Likert scale, with response options of Always (4), Often (3), Seldom (2) and Never (1), focusing on teachers' techniques and resources for integrating reading and writing

instruction. Section C contained a single open-ended question inviting respondents to identify additional techniques and resources used in their teaching that were not captured in Section B.

To establish content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed alongside the research questions and hypotheses by subject-matter experts in the Department of Arts Education and measurement specialists in the Department of Social Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin. The instrument was subsequently revised in accordance with the reviewers' recommendations and feedback before finalisation. Reliability was assessed using the test-retest method. The questionnaire was administered twice to a group of senior secondary English language teachers from schools outside the study sample, with a four-week interval between administrations. Scores from both administrations were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC), yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.76, which is considered acceptable for research instruments of this kind (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

Data collection was administered in person by one of the researchers. Prior to distribution, school principals were contacted with a formal approval letter outlining the research objectives, expected participation and assurances of confidentiality. Participating teachers were briefed on the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation and confidentiality safeguards. Questionnaires did not require respondents to provide their names, thereby ensuring anonymity and encouraging candid responses. Follow-up visits were conducted several days after initial distribution to collect completed questionnaires and minimise attrition. No significant language barriers were encountered, as all participants were qualified English language teachers and the questionnaire was administered in English.

2.4. Data Analysis

Completed questionnaires were manually checked for completeness and consistency before analysis. Incomplete questionnaires were excluded from the dataset, and data were then coded and entered for statistical processing. Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were employed for the quantitative data. Frequencies and percentages were used to describe respondents' demographic characteristics. Mean scores and standard deviations were computed to describe teachers' reported techniques and resources for integrating reading and writing instruction, with a

mean score of 2.50 set as the benchmark for decision-making on each item. Inferential analyses were conducted at a 0.05 alpha level of significance. Independent samples t-tests were used to examine differences between two independent groups, such as those defined by qualification or school type, while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied where comparisons involved more than two groups, for instance those defined by years of teaching experience. These tests are consistent with standard practice for analysing group differences in educational survey research (Field, 2024).

2.5. Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria. The researcher submitted a formal request letter detailing the research purpose, target population, data collection procedures and participating institutions. The department reviewed the submission and granted approval to proceed. All participation was strictly voluntary. School principals and teachers received written information outlining the study's objectives and their expected roles. Participants were informed of their right to decline or withdraw from the study at any stage without consequence. Anonymity was preserved throughout, as no names or identifying information were recorded on questionnaires, and all data were used solely for research purposes. Responses were treated with strict confidentiality and are reported only in aggregate form to prevent the identification of individual participants.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The study sample comprised 167 senior secondary English language teachers from three local government areas in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. Table 1 presents the demographic distribution of respondents. Gender distribution revealed 74 male teachers (44.31 percent) and 93 female teachers (55.69 percent), indicating a slight preponderance of female teachers in the sampled schools. Regarding qualifications (Table 2), respondents held diverse credentials ranging from NCE to Master's degrees. The distribution included 13 teachers (7.78 percent) with NCE qualifications, 57 teachers (34.13 percent) with B.Ed./B.A.Ed., 19 teachers (11.38 percent) with B.A. in English, 21 teachers (12.57 percent) with B.A. English plus PGDE/NCE, 16 teachers (9.58 percent) with M.A. in English, 18 teachers (10.79 percent) with

M.Ed. in English, 9 teachers (5.39 percent) with M.A. English plus PGDE/NCE, and 14 teachers (8.38 percent) in other qualification categories.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents Based on Gender.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	74	44.31
Female	93	55.69
Total	167	100.0

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 2: Distribution of the Respondents Based on Qualification.

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
NCE	13	07.78
B.Ed + B.A.Ed.	57	34.13
B.A. English	19	11.38
B.A. English + PGDE/NCE	21	12.57
M.A. English	16	09.58
M.Ed. English	18	10.79
M.A. English + PGDE/NCE	9	05.39
Others	14	08.38
Total	167	100.0

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Teaching experience (Table 3) varied substantially across the sample. Fifty-one teachers (30.54 percent) possessed between 0-5 years' experience, 40 teachers (23.95 percent) had 6-10 years' experience, while 76 teachers (45.51 percent) had above 10 years' experience, indicating that nearly half the sample

comprised highly experienced educators. Regarding school type (Table 4), 103 respondents (61.68 percent) taught in public secondary schools, while 64 respondents (38.32 percent) worked in private secondary schools.

Table 3: Distribution of the Respondents Based on Experience.

Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
0-5 years	51	30.54
6-10 years	40	23.95
Above 10 years	76	45.51
Total	167	100.0

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 4: Distribution of the Respondents Based on School Type.

School Type	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Public	103	61.68
Private	64	38.32
Total	167	100.0

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Research Question 1: What techniques do senior secondary school English teachers employ in using reading to teach writing in Ogbomoso, Nigeria?

Table 5: Mean And Standard Deviation of Techniques Senior Secondary School English Teachers Employ in Using Reading to Teach Writing in Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

S/N	Techniques	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	Reading Models: I expose students to various text types to understand structure and features before writing.	3.52	0.66	Always
2	Reading-Writing Integration: I guide students through pre-reading, reading and post-reading activities that lead to writing tasks.	3.52	0.74	Always
3	Text Analysis: I help students analyse reading texts to understand organisation and language features for writing.	3.49	0.64	Often
4	Collaborative Learning: I use pair/group work for students to discuss readings and provide peer feedback on writing.	3.22	0.83	Often
5	Text Framework: I provide reading-based outlines and templates to support student writing. 3.37	0.75	Often	
6	Differentiated Tasks: I assign varied reading and writing tasks based on students' abilities and needs.	3.50	0.69	Always

7	Reading Response: I use reading texts as prompts for creative and analytical writing tasks.	3.48	0.68	Often
8	Text Organisation: I teach students to use reading texts to understand coherence and organisation in writing.	3.57	0.57	Always
9	Individual Guidance: I provide one-on-one feedback on students' written responses to readings.	3.45	0.62	Often
10	Digital Integration: I use online tools to help students connect reading and writing activities.	3.19	0.87	Often
11	Think-Aloud: I demonstrate how to extract writing ideas and patterns from reading texts.	3.47	0.66	Often
12	Reading Discussion: I facilitate discussions about texts before assigning related writing tasks.	3.60	0.59	Always
Weighted Mean		3.45		

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 5 presents the mean scores and standard deviations for techniques teachers employ in integrating reading and writing instruction. The overall weighted mean for techniques was 3.45, indicating that teachers "often" to "always" employ these approaches. Reading Discussion recorded the highest mean score ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 0.59$), establishing it as the most frequently used technique for connecting reading and writing. Text Organisation closely followed ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.57$), indicating teachers frequently guide students to understand how reading texts model coherence and organisation principles applicable to writing. Reading Models and Reading-Writing Integration both achieved mean scores of 3.52 ($SD = 0.66$ and 0.74 respectively), suggesting teachers regularly expose students to text exemplars and guide them through pre-reading, reading and post-reading activities leading to writing tasks. Differentiated Tasks also ranked highly with mean score of 3.50 ($SD = 0.69$), demonstrating that teachers consistently assign varied reading and writing activities aligned to differing student abilities.

Additional techniques, while slightly lower, remained within the "often used" range. Text Analysis achieved a mean of 3.49 ($SD = 0.64$), indicating regular teacher engagement in helping students analyse reading texts to understand

organisation and language features applicable to writing. Reading Response ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 0.68$) demonstrated frequent use of texts as prompts for creative and analytical writing. Think-Aloud ($M = 3.47$, $SD = 0.66$) indicated teachers regularly demonstrate extraction of writing ideas and patterns from reading texts. Individual Guidance ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 0.62$) showed consistent provision of one-on-one feedback on students' written responses to readings. Text Framework ($M = 3.37$, $SD = 0.75$) revealed moderate frequent use of reading-based outlines and templates supporting student writing.

Techniques with relatively lower mean scores, while still within the "often used" range, included Collaborative Learning ($M = 3.22$, $SD = 0.83$) and Digital Integration ($M = 3.19$, $SD = 0.87$). These findings indicate that although pair and group work for discussing readings and providing peer feedback occur with some regularity, and online tools for connecting reading and writing activities are employed, these approaches receive less consistent emphasis compared to more traditional, teacher-directed strategies such as reading discussion and text analysis.

Research Question 2: What resources do senior secondary school English teachers employ in using reading to teach writing in Ogbomosho, Nigeria?

Table 6: Mean And Standard Deviation of Resources Senior Secondary School English Teachers Employ in Using Reading to Teach Writing in Ogbomosho, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
13	I use the English curriculum to integrate reading and writing instruction.	3.78	0.50	Always
14	I utilise various English textbooks and workbooks that combine reading and writing activities.	3.61	0.60	Always
15	I incorporate WAEC and NECO past questions to practice both reading comprehension and writing tasks.	3.55	0.62	Always
16	I guide students to use educational websites (e.g., British Council's Learn English) for reading-writing practice.	3.14	0.95	Often
17	I assign integrated reading-writing exercises from English workbooks. 3.43	0.70	Often	
18	I use the English curriculum to plan lessons that connect reading with writing skills.	3.62	0.56	Always
19	I use literature texts to help students analyse writing styles and develop vocabulary for their own writing.	3.55	0.68	Always

20	I facilitate participation in writing clubs and workshops where students discuss readings and practice writing.	3.33	0.76	Often
Weighted Mean		3.50		

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 6 presents mean scores and standard deviations for resources teachers employ when integrating reading and writing instruction. The overall weighted mean for resources was 3.50, indicating that teachers "often" to "always" rely on core instructional materials. The English Curriculum achieved the highest mean score (M = 3.78, SD = 0.50) for integrating reading and writing, and a closely related mean of 3.62 (SD = 0.56) for lesson planning that connects reading with writing skills. These findings establish the curriculum as the primary and most authoritative guide actively shaping how teachers design lessons linking reading activities to writing tasks.

English textbooks and workbooks recorded a mean score of 3.61 (SD = 0.60), indicating teachers consistently utilise approved textbook materials. Literature texts achieved a mean of 3.55 (SD = 0.68), demonstrating regular teacher use of literary works to help students analyse writing styles and develop vocabulary for their own writing. WAEC and NECO past questions scored 3.55 (SD = 0.62), showing strong reliance on examination practice materials reflecting teachers' emphasis on preparing students for high-stakes assessments alongside modelling effective writing.

Additional resources also featured prominently. Integrated reading-writing exercises from English workbooks achieved a mean of 3.43 (SD = 0.70), indicating regular assignment of structured practice materials. Participation in writing clubs and workshops scored 3.33 (SD = 0.76), suggesting

teachers moderately encourage co-curricular enrichment activities where students discuss readings and practise writing beyond formal classroom instruction.

The least frequently used resource was educational websites, with a mean of 3.14 (SD = 0.95). Although this falls within the "often" category, it represents notably lower usage compared to other resources. This finding indicates that while some teachers incorporate digital platforms such as the British Council's Learn English website, reliance on online educational resources remains limited compared to printed and officially recommended materials.

3.2. Hypothesis Testing

3.2.1. Hypotheses 1 And 2: Influence of Teacher Qualification on Techniques and Resources

The first hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of teachers' qualifications on the technique employed in using reading to teach writing.* One-way ANOVA analysis (Table 7) examining differences in techniques based on teacher qualification yielded an F-value of 6.271 with significance value of 0.00, well below the 0.05 alpha level. This result indicates a statistically significant difference in technique usage across qualification categories. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that teacher qualifications significantly influence the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing.

Table 7: One-Way ANOVA Analysis Showing the Difference in the Technique Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on Qualification ANOVA.

Techniques	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1172.129	7	167.447			
Within Groups	3791.444	159	26.700	6.271	.000	Rejected
Total	4963.573	166				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 8: Post-Hoc Table Showing the Differences in Mean Scores of Teachers' Use of Techniques Based on Their Qualification.

Duncan^{a,b}

Qualification	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05			
		1	2	3	4
Others	14	35.3333			
NCE	13	37.0000	37.0000		
M. Ed	18	38.8125	38.8125	38.8125	
M.A. English	16		40.2500	40.2500	
B.A. English + PGDE/NCE	21			42.4737	42.4737
B.Ed.	57			42.8077	42.8077
M.A. English + PGDE/NCE	9			43.0000	43.0000
B.A. English	19			45.1579	

Sig.	.102	.127	.063	.227	
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Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Post-hoc analysis (Table 8) revealed the mean scores of teachers with different qualifications. Teachers holding a B.A. in English degree achieved the highest mean score (M = 45.16), demonstrating substantially greater technique usage than colleagues with other qualifications. Homogeneous subsets indicate that teachers with unspecified qualifications ("Others") demonstrated the lowest technique usage (M = 35.33), followed by NCE holders (M = 37.00). Teachers with M.Ed. credentials (M = 38.81) and M.A. English graduates (M = 40.25) showed moderate proficiency. Teachers with combined subject and pedagogical qualifications – B.A. English with PGDE/NCE (M = 42.47), B.Ed. graduates (M = 42.81), and M.A. English with PGDE/NCE (M = 43.00) – demonstrated substantially higher technique application than those with basic qualifications

alone. The pattern establishes that subject-specific expertise, particularly in English, combined with pedagogical preparation, facilitates sophisticated technique application in reading-based writing instruction.

The second hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of teachers' qualifications on the resources employed in using reading to teach writing.* One-way ANOVA analysis (Table 9) yielded an F-value with significance value of 0.00, below the 0.05 alpha level, indicating a statistically significant difference in resource usage across qualification categories. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that teacher qualifications significantly influence the resources employed in reading-based writing instruction.

Table 9: One-Way ANOVA Analysis Showing the Difference in the Resources Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on Qualification ANOVA.

Resources	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	348.417	7	49.774			
Within Groups	1383.556	159	9.743	5.109	.000	Rejected
Total	1731.973	166				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Table 10: Post-Hoc Table Showing the Differences in Mean Scores of Teachers' Use of Resources Based on Their Qualification.

**Resources
Duncan^{a,b}**

Qualification	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05		
		1	2	3
Others	14	24.6667		
M.Ed.	18	26.3750	26.3750	
NCE	13	26.4000	26.4000	
M.A. English	16	27.1250	27.1250	
M.A. English + PGDE/NCE	9		28.3333	28.3333
B.A. English + PGDE/NCE	21		28.6316	28.6316
B.Ed.	57		28.8077	28.8077
B.A. English	19			30.2105
Sig.		.064	.080	.161

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Post-hoc analysis (Table 10) showed that teachers with B.A. in English achieved the highest mean score (M = 30.21) in resource utilisation, again demonstrating superior performance compared to colleagues with other qualifications. The pattern of qualification influence on resource use paralleled that observed for techniques, with basic qualifications associated with lowest resource use and subject-specific degrees associated with broadest resource utilisation. This finding indicates that teacher qualification substantially determines the range and frequency of instructional resources employed.

3.2.2. Hypotheses 3 And 4: Influence of School Type on Techniques and Resources

The third hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of school types on the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing.* Independent samples t-test analysis (Table 11) comparing public and private school teachers revealed a calculated significance value of 0.241, substantially greater than the 0.05 alpha level. The mean score for public school teachers was 41.07 (SD = 6.16) while private school teachers achieved a mean of 42.25 (SD = 4.49). Although private school teachers demonstrated a numerically higher mean, the difference was not statistically

significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, confirming that school type does not significantly influence the techniques teachers

employ in using reading to teach writing. Teachers in both public and private secondary schools employ reading-based writing techniques to similar extents.

Table 11: Independent Sample T-Test Showing the Difference in the Techniques Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on School Type.

Variable	School Type	N	Mean	Std. D	df	T	Sig.	Decision
Techniques	Public	103	41.07	6.16	148	-1.177	0.241	Accepted
	Private	64	42.25	4.49				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

The fourth hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of school types on the resources employed in using reading to teach writing.* Independent samples t-test analysis (Table 12) yielded a significance value of 0.766, well above the 0.05 alpha level. The mean score for public school teachers was 28.06 (SD = 3.56) while private school teachers achieved a mean of 27.88 (SD = 2.98). The difference between these means was not

statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, confirming that school type does not significantly influence the resources teachers employ in using reading to teach writing. The proprietorship of a school, whether public or private, does not substantially determine the kind of resources teachers employ when integrating reading and writing instruction.

Table 12: Independent Sample T-Test Showing the Difference in the Resources Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on School Type.

Variable	School Type	N	Mean	Std. D	df	T	Sig.	Decision
Resources	Public	103	28.06	3.56	148	0.299	0.766	Accepted
	Private	64	27.88	2.98				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

3.2.3. Hypotheses 5 And 6: Influence of Teaching Experience on Techniques and Resources

The fifth hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of teachers experience on the techniques employed in using reading to teach writing.* One-way ANOVA analysis (Table 13) comparing technique usage across experience categories yielded a

significance value of 0.004, below the 0.05 alpha level, indicating statistically significant differences. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that teaching experience significantly influences the techniques employed in reading-based writing instruction.

Table 13: One-Way ANOVA Showing the Difference in the Resources Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on Qualification.

ANOVA						
Techniques	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	359.529	2	179.764	5.740	0.004	Rejected
Within Groups	4604.044	164	31.320			
Total	4963.573	166				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Post-hoc analysis (Table 14) revealed the mean scores for each experience category. Teachers with above 10 years' experience achieved the highest mean score (M = 42.82), followed by teachers with 6-10 years' experience (M = 41.43), while teachers with 0-5 years' experience demonstrated the lowest mean score (M = 39.12). This pattern indicates that as

teachers accumulate experience, they employ more varied and sophisticated techniques for connecting reading and writing instruction, with the most substantial differences occurring between novice teachers (0-5 years) and moderately experienced teachers (6-10 years), with further modest gains for highly experienced teachers (above 10 years).

Table 14: Post-Hoc Table Showing the Differences in Mean Scores of Teachers' Use of Techniques Based on Teacher Experience.

Experience	N	Techniques Duncan ^{a,b}	
		Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2

1-5 years	51	39.1163	
6-10 years	40		41.4250
Above 10 years	76		42.8209
Sig.		1.000	.226

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

The sixth hypothesis stated: *There is no significant influence of teachers' experience on the resources employed in using reading to teach writing.* One-way ANOVA analysis (Table 15) yielded a significance value of 0.003, below the 0.05 alpha level, indicating

statistically significant differences in resource usage across experience categories. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that teaching experience significantly influences the resources employed in reading-based writing instruction.

Table 15: One-Way ANOVA Showing the Difference in the Resources Teachers Employed in Using Reading to Teach Writing Based on Qualification.

Resources	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	135.505	2	67.752	6.239	0.003	
Within Groups	1596.469	164	10.860			Rejected
Total	1731.973	166				

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

Post-hoc analysis (Table 16) showed that teachers with above 10 years' experience achieved the highest mean score (M = 29.04) in resource utilisation, substantially exceeding teachers with 6-10 years' experience (M = 27.48) and those with 0-5 years' experience (M = 26.91). These findings indicate that

experienced teachers access and utilise a broader range of instructional resources than less experienced colleagues, suggesting that accumulated experience enables teachers to develop more extensive resource networks and awareness of available materials for reading-based writing instruction.

Table 16: Post-Hoc Table Showing the Differences in Mean Scores of Teachers' Use of Techniques Based on Their Qualification.

Experience	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
1-5 years	51	26.9070	
6-10 years	40	27.4750	
Above 10 years	76		29.0448
Sig.		.402	1.000

Researcher's SPSS output 2025

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study examined the techniques and resources senior secondary English teachers in Ogbomoso employ when integrating reading and writing instruction, with particular focus on how teacher qualifications, school type and teaching experience influence these pedagogical choices. Four key findings emerged from the analysis. First, teachers in Ogbomoso employ a wide range of techniques for reading-based writing instruction (weighted mean 3.45), with reading discussion, text organisation and reading models most frequently employed. Second, teachers consistently utilise core instructional resources (weighted mean 3.50), relying primarily on the English curriculum, textbooks and literature texts. Third, teacher qualifications significantly predict both the techniques employed and resources utilised, with subject-specific qualifications enabling substantially more varied

instructional approaches. Fourth, teaching experience significantly predicts both technique and resource usage, with teachers possessing over ten years' experience employing substantially more varied approaches than less experienced colleagues. Notably, school type (public versus private) did not significantly influence either technique or resource selection.

The finding that teachers employ a rich array of techniques with overall high usage frequency aligns with existing knowledge regarding teacher professionalism in Nigerian secondary education. Teachers demonstrate strong pedagogical orientations towards text-based analysis and discussion-oriented activities, consistent with genre theory (Hyland, 2004) and contemporary literacy instruction principles. The prominence of reading discussion, text organisation and reading models reflects teachers' understanding that analysing and discussing texts before writing helps students

internalise rhetorical structures and linguistic features, practices empirically demonstrated to improve writing development (Graham & Hebert, 2011). This suggests that despite systemic constraints, teachers maintain commitment to evidence-based instructional practices that effectively connect reading and writing.

The strong reliance on traditional and official resources is particularly significant. The English curriculum's highest utilisation rating (mean 3.78) underscores its authoritative role in shaping instructional decisions. The high utilisation of textbooks (mean 3.61) and examination past questions (mean 3.55) reflects the pervasive influence of national examinations (WAEC and NECO) on classroom practice, a phenomenon extensively documented in Nigerian educational literature (Taura & Ibrahim, 2023). Rather than representing pedagogical limitation, this finding reflects the systemic reality that teachers must balance curriculum implementation with examination preparation demands. Understanding this context is essential for interpreting resource utilisation patterns without ascribing deficit perspectives to teacher practice.

The statistically significant influence of teacher qualifications on both techniques and resources employed represents a substantial finding with important implications. Teachers holding B.A. in English degrees demonstrated substantially higher technique usage (mean 45.16) compared to colleagues with basic qualifications such as NCE (mean 37.00) or unspecified qualifications (mean 35.33). Similarly, B.A. English holders achieved the highest resource utilisation scores (mean 30.21) substantially exceeding those with basic qualifications (NCE mean 26.40, Other mean 24.67). This finding aligns with established understanding of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), where subject-specific expertise directly enhances instructional quality (Depaepe et al., 2013). Teachers with strong subject matter expertise in English possess deeper knowledge of textual analysis, literary styles, linguistic patterns and diverse pedagogical resources that they strategically draw upon to make explicit the connections between reading practices and writing applications. Specifically, teachers with B.A. in English degrees recognise how specific reading techniques (for example, analysing author's rhetorical choices in a literary text) transfer to writing applications (for example, deliberately employing similar rhetorical choices in students' own compositions), whereas teachers with basic qualifications may focus on

generic reading and writing activities without highlighting these disciplinary connections. The finding further supports research establishing positive correlations between teacher subject qualifications and student achievement in language arts (Wayne & Youngs, 2003; Hill, Rowan & Ball, 2005). In addition, teachers holding combined subject and pedagogical qualifications (B.A. English with PGDE/NCE, M.A. English with PGDE/NCE) demonstrated substantially higher scores than those with subject qualifications alone ($M = 43.00$ and 42.47 respectively, compared to $M = 40.25$ for M.A. English holders without pedagogical qualifications). This pattern suggests that integration of pedagogical training with subject expertise produces synergistic effects on instructional quality. Whilst subject knowledge enables recognition of reading-writing connections, pedagogical training equips teachers with instructional strategies for revealing these connections to learners, creating multiplicative rather than additive effects on teaching sophistication. This pattern indicates that teacher preparation programs combining rigorous subject matter preparation with contemporary pedagogical training enable educators to implement more sophisticated and varied instructional approaches.

The finding that school type does not significantly influence technique or resource selection is noteworthy and counterintuitive, challenging common assumptions about substantive pedagogical differences between public and private sectors. This non-finding requires careful interpretation, as it does not suggest equivalence in resource availability or school infrastructure, but rather indicates that despite differing material conditions, teachers select similar instructional approaches. Independent samples t-tests revealed no significant differences in technique usage (public mean 41.07, private mean 42.25, $p = 0.241$) or resource utilisation (public mean 28.06, private mean 27.88, $p = 0.766$) between school types. This finding suggests that the centralised national curriculum and standardised examination system create homogenising effects on teaching practices across school sectors. Both public and private schools operate within the same systemic expectations and assessment frameworks, producing convergence in instructional approaches regardless of proprietorship (Chinenye et al., 2025). This indicates that systemic factors, particularly curriculum requirements and examination pressures, exercise more influential effects on teacher practice than school type per se. The finding does not suggest equivalence in resource availability between school types. Rather, it indicates that despite potentially

different material resources, teachers select similar techniques and utilise available resources comparably to address curriculum and assessment demands.

The significant positive influence of teaching experience on both technique and resource usage substantiates understanding of teacher development as a continuous process. Teachers with over ten years of experience achieved significantly higher mean scores for techniques (mean 42.82) and resources (mean 29.04) compared to those with 6-10 years of experience (techniques 41.43, resources 27.48) and 0-5 years of experience (techniques 39.12, resources 26.91). These findings align with research demonstrating that sustained practice enables accumulation of diverse instructional strategies and development of practical wisdom enabling their contextually appropriate implementation (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Specifically, experienced teachers have navigated varied classroom scenarios, encountered diverse learner needs and received feedback on multiple instructional approaches, enabling them to develop refined mental models of when different reading-based writing techniques are appropriate and how to implement them effectively with particular student populations. Experienced teachers have navigated diverse classroom scenarios and student populations, refining their instructional approaches through iterative practice. However, the pattern of differences suggests the relationship is non-linear; the most substantial gains occur between novice and moderately experienced teachers, with more modest improvements for highly experienced teachers. This pattern indicates that the relationship between experience and instructional sophistication is not linearly cumulative. Rather, experience appears to establish a foundation of competence substantially beyond novice levels, yet continued advancement beyond approximately ten years requires deliberate engagement with new pedagogical approaches, updated curriculum frameworks and contemporary literacy research. Continued professional development for established teachers remains necessary, as experience alone may plateau without systematic professional learning.

This study possesses several methodological strengths. The research employed a purposive sampling strategy capturing all 167 English language teachers across three local government areas, providing comprehensive representation of the teacher population in Ogbomoso. The use of a validated instrument with established reliability (test-retest correlation 0.76) and validity procedures ensures measurement credibility. The mixed-method

design, combining quantitative data addressing research questions with qualitative insights from open-ended responses, provides triangulation strengthening interpretation. The use of appropriate statistical tests, such as one-way ANOVA with post-hoc comparisons and independent samples t-tests enables valid hypothesis testing with adequate alpha levels.

However, several limitations deserve to be recognised. As a descriptive survey, the study captures teachers' self-reported practices rather than observed classroom behaviour, potentially introducing response bias or social desirability effects. Teachers may overestimate technique frequency or resource utilisation when reporting, particularly regarding techniques perceived as pedagogically desirable. The cross-sectional design provides snapshot evidence rather than longitudinal data tracking practice changes over time. In addition, while the study examined three teacher characteristics (qualification, experience, school type), it did not investigate other potentially influential factors such as teachers' beliefs about literacy instruction, school leadership support, or professional development access. The geographic focus on Ogbomoso limits generalisability to other Nigerian contexts, though the semi-urban setting and school type distribution may provide reasonable representation of similar educational environments. Finally, the sample comprised volunteers willing to participate, potentially including teachers more engaged with professional development than those declining participation.

This study generates important implications for teacher professional development policy and practice. The finding that teacher qualifications significantly predict instructional quality suggests substantial benefit from policies prioritising teacher qualification improvement. Many teachers holding basic qualifications (NCE) or non-standard credentials demonstrate substantially lower technique and resource utilisation. Policy initiatives promoting advancement to degree-level qualifications, particularly B.A. in English or combined pedagogical-subject programmes, offer potential for enhancing instructional quality. Given that teachers with basic qualifications demonstrate substantially lower technique usage (NCE mean 37.00 versus B.A. English mean 45.16), the Ministry of Education should prioritise policies facilitating access to higher qualification programmes through distance learning, sandwich programmes or tuition support. Such initiatives should particularly target early-career teachers in public schools who may lack

degree-level credentials. The substantial performance differential (8-point mean score difference) suggests that qualification advancement offers significant potential for improving instructional quality across the system.

The significant relationship between teaching experience and instructional quality suggests benefit from structured mentoring programmes pairing experienced and novice teachers. Rather than assuming experience automatically develops competence, deliberate mentoring relationships enable knowledge transfer and accelerated professional development for less experienced teachers. Schools should establish formal professional learning communities wherein experienced teachers with sophisticated pedagogical repertoires mentor colleagues, sharing effective techniques and resource utilisation strategies. The finding that school type does not significantly influence practice suggests that systemic interventions benefiting all schools equally are appropriate. Rather than differentially supporting private schools, policy should target resource constraints affecting both public and private institutions. Specifically, curriculum materials, reading resources and teacher professional development opportunities should be equitably distributed across school sectors.

The consistently lower utilisation of digital resources (educational websites mean 3.14) despite documented theoretical benefits of technology-enhanced literacy instruction suggests barriers operating at the systemic rather than individual teacher level. Rather than reflecting teacher reluctance or insufficient pedagogical knowledge, this pattern points to infrastructure constraints including inadequate computer access in schools, limited internet connectivity stability and insufficient technical training. Notably, qualification and experience do not significantly predict digital resource use, suggesting teachers would incorporate these resources with appropriate systemic support. Policy interventions addressing infrastructure limitations would enable broader digital resource integration regardless of teacher characteristics. Similarly, the strong reliance on examination materials reflects systemic realities rather than pedagogical limitation, and so rather than discouraging examination preparation, policy should ensure that examination-oriented teaching incorporates contemporary literacy instruction principles. Teacher development programmes should emphasise that reading-based writing techniques enhance examination performance while

developing deeper literacy competencies.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examined the techniques and resources senior secondary English teachers in Ogbomoso employ when integrating reading and writing instruction and how teacher qualifications, school type and teaching experience influence these pedagogical choices. The research addressed eight objectives through systematic investigation of 167 teachers across three local government areas. Teachers in Ogbomoso actively employ reading-based writing instruction using varied techniques and resources. Teachers consistently implement reading discussion, text organisation and reading models as primary techniques, indicating strong pedagogical understanding of how texts function as writing models. Resource utilisation centres on the English curriculum, textbooks and literature texts, with examination materials serving as secondary resources. These reveals committed practitioners implementing integrated literacy instruction within curriculum bound, examination focused constraints.

A significant finding emerged regarding teacher qualifications. Teachers with subject specific qualifications, particularly B.A. in English degrees, demonstrate substantially more varied and sophisticated instructional approaches than those with basic teaching qualifications. The combination of subject knowledge with pedagogical preparation proves particularly powerful in enabling rich instruction. This underscores the critical importance of subject matter expertise in enabling effective teaching. Teaching experience significantly influences both technique selection and resource utilisation. Teachers with extended experience demonstrate more varied instructional approaches and access broader ranges of resources than less experienced colleagues. The positive relationship between experience and instructional sophistication suggests that sustained engagement with classroom practice enables accumulation of strategies and practical wisdom. However, the relationship is non-linear, indicating that deliberate professional engagement remains necessary for continued development.

School type does not significantly influence technique selection or resource utilisation. This finding challenges assumptions about pedagogical differences between public and private sectors. Rather, centralised curriculum mandates and standardised examinations create convergent pressures on instructional practice regardless of school proprietorship. Systemic factors matter more

than school type for determining instructional approaches. The findings paint a portrait of English language teaching characterised by professional commitment and evidence-based practices. Teacher qualifications and experience are critical policy levers for improving instruction. Investments in teacher education that combine robust subject matter knowledge with contemporary pedagogical training enable substantially more sophisticated reading-based writing instruction. The finding that B.A. in English holders demonstrate significantly higher instructional sophistication than NCE holders suggests that subject-specific expertise, combined with pedagogical preparation, represents a critical lever for improving instructional quality system-wide. Recognition of experience as a significant predictor suggests benefit from deliberate career progression pathways and mentoring structures.

Future research should investigate the

mechanisms through which qualifications influence practice, specifically whether knowledge differences, confidence differences or access to professional networks differ across qualification categories, as well as whether the experience-effectiveness relationship operates similarly across public and private school contexts. Observational studies examining actual technique implementation in classrooms would strengthen understanding beyond self-reported frequency data, while longitudinal studies tracking practice changes would illuminate how interventions affect instructional quality over time. Replication of the study in other Nigerian zones would establish whether findings generalise beyond Ogbomoso. Policy makers should recognise that instructional quality can be developed through strategic qualification advancement and supported experience rather than being fixed by school type.

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